

STEPS OF FORMATION OF DIFFERENTIATED TEACHING IN PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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Abstract. The article considers the characteristic features of the retrospective development of differentiated education in our country, analyzes theoretical sources containing historical and pedagogical research on this problem, describes the stages of formation of profile differentiation in the direction of pedagogical training in order to increase the efficiency and optimize the learning process of future specialists. Based on the periodizations of differentiated learning existing in pedagogical science and the analysis of theoretical sources, a periodization of the development of differentiated learning in pedagogy is proposed, reflecting a historical and logical view of this pedagogical phenomenon.

Keywords: differentiated training; profile orientation; individualization; department; training center at the university; training of future specialists, the system of training specialists.

Introduction. Changes in the socio-economic and political life of modern society, the humanistic concept and the “restructuring of the higher education system at all levels” determine the search for further ways to develop differentiated education. The analysis of the accumulated historical and pedagogical experience is necessary to increase the effectiveness of the development of individual educational trajectories and create pedagogical conditions for the comprehensive development of the personality of students of higher educational institutions. The insufficient number of historical and pedagogical studies on the problem of differentiated education, taking into account the profile specifics of training future specialists in universities and the lack of generalization of experience on this issue prevents the successful implementation of differentiated education in departments and training centers of universities, does not allow taking into account the individual characteristics of students in full [2, p. 192].

The scientific understanding of the development of differentiated learning in the modern domestic educational space, the analysis of the acquired experience and traditions is relevant in order to determine new prospects for the development of specialized education, the development of innovative concepts for the organization of differentiated learning, taking into account interdisciplinary and competence-based approaches to higher education.

Object of the research and methods. The majority of scientific works on the problems of the formation of differentiated education are devoted to the study of this process at school, “school business” [3, p. 180], “is mainly connected with the educational process of secondary schools” [2, p. 206]. The space of higher educational institutions is still not fully explored; the historical periods of the development of the pedagogical theory of specialized education are insufficiently represented, taking into account the specifics of training future specialists in universities. In this regard, the features and trends in the development of differentiated teaching of pedagogical students in universities have not been fully identified and require further research.

In the works of researchers, the concept of “differentiated learning” does not have an unambiguous definition due to the lack of a single terminological apparatus on this issue. In English, the term “differentiation” (“difference”) means difference, separation, differentiation, distinguishing feature, isolation, modification.

K.G. Selevko defines differentiated learning as a form of organization of the educational process, when a teacher works with a homogeneous group of students who have common qualities that are significant for the educational process and as part of a common didactic system in the space of which the specialization of teaching of various groups of students is realized [1, p. 229].

A.A. Kirsanov understands differentiated learning as “a system of educational and didactic means that correspond to the goals of activity and the real cognitive capabilities of the class collective, individual students and groups of students, allowing for the student’s educational activity at the level of his potential, taking into account the learning goals” [4, p. 138].

Analyzing the features of the development of differentiated learning, researcher V.I. Pisarenko rightly notes that “a personality-oriented approach is considered as an alternative to the traditional socio-oriented one” [9, p. 99], and the implementation of learning goals should be carried out within the framework of a personality-oriented paradigm based on communicative, competence-based, professionally-oriented and stylistic approaches.

V.A. Romanov, considering the integration of special disciplines of the department and general disciplines of a university, notes the importance of implementing in practice the selection of “the content of special training of students taking into account their individual characteristics and needs” [11, p. 256].

The period of pre-revolutionary formation. At this period, the issues of the differentiated approach have not yet been studied in a special way [6, p. 180]. The research of P.V. Bezobrazov, M. Bogolepov, M.I. Demkov, A.K. Klopov is aimed at analyzing the works of such outstanding educators as V.G. Belinsky, N.I. Pirogov, K.D. Ushinsky, L.N. Tolstoy devoted to school education [6, 181]. The characteristic features of pedagogical experience are contained in the works of A.V. Andriyanov, M.I. Dragomirov, M.I. Kutuzov, S.O. Makarov, A.V. Suvorov, D.F. Ushakov.

The Soviet period is characterized by both the rise and decline of the differentiated learning process. In the 20s, the differentiation of training in schools deepened, taking into account the specifics of the professional direction, specialty.

In the second half of the 20s, the first educational formations were formed at universities, such as Lomonosov Moscow State University and others.

The 30-40 years are characterized by some stagnation of the ideas of differentiated education, scientific views on a unified form of education are popular in educational institutions. The problem of differentiation of education becomes relevant again in the early 50s with the aim of specialized training of teaching staff.

A.V. Reznik notes that at the end of 1941, the State Research Institute of Schools of the People's Commissariat of Education began issuing methodological manuals for subject teachers "Physical Education at school", "Elements in teaching mathematics, physics, chemistry, geography", "Physical education of students", etc. From the middle of 1942-1943, other academic subjects were included in the curricula of secondary schools. Students studied primary physical training in grades I-IV and physical education in grades V-X.

The period of perestroika (the end of the 80s). There is an intensive development of educational and production complexes, some of them are being opened at specialized industrial enterprises, the work of lyceums and gymnasiums is being rebuilt taking into account the professionalization of training.

The second half of the 80s and 90s are characterized by the emergence of a large number of studies not only on the problems of differentiated learning, but also affecting the development of the student's personality, abilities and interests (V.I. Zagvyazinsky, A.K. Markova, V.M. Monakhov, etc.).

The period from the 90s of the XX century to the present. The beginning of the 90s is considered as an intensive stage in the development of the system of pedagogical training in universities. This is the appearance of a large number of complex psychological and pedagogical studies on the problems of education, the study of domestic and foreign experience, “the process of gradual transition from a unitary educational system to a democratic, variable one has begun” .

Results and their analysis. In the senior classes of secondary school and in higher educational institutions, training is carried out according to developed and approved educational and methodological plans. Among the large number of works of this period, the studies of E.V. Bondarevskaya, P.Ya. Galperin, I.A. Zimnaya, A.N. Leontiev, V.M. Monakhov, V.A. Orlov, I.M. Osmolovskaya, S.L. Rubinstein, I.S. Yakimanskaya, V.Ya. Yakunin should be noted.

The features of the educational process in higher educational institutions of pedagogical profile were studied by V.A. Bodrov, S.M. Godnik, V.M. Korovin, V.S. Listengarten, V.S. Merlin. In the educational process of the university, an important role is assigned to individually differentiated training, level differentiation of educational and methodological complexes of disciplines, there is not always justified fragmentation of specialties. In this regard, S.M. Godnik and V.S. Listengarten rightly notes that “a certain and even initially excessive differentiation creates conditions for new integration and, consequently, development” [4, p. 28].

Conclusion. Currently, the changes taking place in the system of the education affect such significant problems as the terms of recruitment issues, the emergence of new technical equipment and information support, the need to take into account the features of multi-level education in universities (bachelor’s- master’s- postgraduate studies). These changes have an impact on the system of differentiated training of specialists in universities. The problem of differentiated training of students in pedagogical departments of universities requires further historical and pedagogical reflection, search for directions for effective development, modernization and development of new approaches to training and professional development of future specialists.

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